

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

CONCEPTUAL PROVISIONS OF THE FORMATION OF INNOVATIVE ENVIRONMENT IN UZBEKISTAN

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КОНЦЕПТУАЛЬНЫЕ ПОЛОЖЕНИЯ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ИННОВАЦИОННОЙ СРЕДЫ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ

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Abstract

The article deals with the problems of introducing an innovative environment, in particular, the main directions of forming an innovative environment in a strategically oriented economic system. The modern conditions for the transition of economic development to the innovation path are shown. The question of the formation and development of the innovation environment as a determining factor for the sustainable development of the innovation economy is considered

Аннотация

В статье рассматриваются проблемы внедрения инновационной среды, в частности, основные направления формирования инновационной среды в стратегически ориентированной экономической системе. Показаны современные условия перехода развития экономики на инновационный путь. Рассмотрен вопрос о формировании и развитии инновационной среды как определяющего фактора устойчивого развития инновационной экономики

Keywords: innovation environment, innovation systems, innovation economy, economic growth, elements of the innovation environment

Ключевые слова: инновационная среда, инновационные системы, инновационная экономика, экономический рост, элементы инновационной среды

The transition from one type of development of economic systems to another means the need to move from one management institution to another. At the same time, there is a need for a comprehensive study, formation and development of institutions for infrastructural support for the innovative development of economic systems, which makes it possible to identify trends in the convergence of auxiliary and production sectors and eliminate the existing gaps between them. Along with the innovation infrastructure, the innovation environment becomes an additional social productive force.

In modern conditions, the formation and development of the innovation environment is becoming a determining factor in the sustainable development of the innovation economy, which is associated with the use of the results of scientific research and development to create fundamentally new types of products, the creation and application of new technologies for its production with subsequent implementation and sale on the market.

Today, most countries of the world set themselves the task of transitioning to an innovative economy based on knowledge, in which the creation, transfer and use of the results of scientific and technical activities

are the main conditions for sustainable economic growth. Therefore, in sovereign Uzbekistan, since the first days of independence, much attention has been paid to the development of domestic science, leading scientific schools and innovative research.

Today, as world experience shows, there is no alternative to the innovative way of development. The creation, implementation and wide distribution of new products, services of technological processes are becoming key factors in economic growth, improving the efficiency of economic activity and the competitiveness of enterprises. The modernization of the economy, declared one of the main goals of the macroeconomic policy of our state, involves overcoming the country's accelerating technological lag behind world innovation leaders.

Innovativeness is becoming an integral characteristic of the modern economy; this applies equally to states and their communities, as well as to individual companies. Innovative orientation is an imperative not only of today, but also of the near future of human activity in any field.

For Uzbekistan today, the transition to an innovative type of economic development, which requires the

full disclosure of the national scientific and technical potential, is especially relevant.

The purpose, objectives of the state policy in the development of the country's innovation system, the mechanisms and main measures for its implementation are currently defined in the main directions of innovation policy in the development of the innovation system, considered as a set of subjects and objects of innovation, interacting in the process of creating and implementing an innovation system. products and operating within the framework of the state policy in the field of innovation system development.

Modern conditions for the transition of economic development to an innovative path involve the formation of such an innovative environment that would meet all the needs arising from changes in the unstable and socio-economic system and its future development.

The very concept of "innovation environment" appeared in the 1980s and was described by Manuel Castells as a means of analyzing the systemic conditions provided to economic entities for the production of new ideas, products, the creation of new industries and the development of new markets.

There are a fairly large number of interpretations, definitions of the concept of "innovation environment", "however, they all come down to a common feature - this is the environment of the participant in the innovation process, which affects his innovation activity" [3].

Thus, it is believed that the innovation environment is a measure of readiness to perform tasks that ensure the achievement of the set innovation goal, i.e. a measure of readiness for the implementation of an innovative project or program of innovative transformations and, consequently, the introduction of innovations.

Another definition of the innovation environment makes it possible to evaluate it as a set of various types of resources, including material, production, financial, intellectual, scientific, technical and other resources necessary for the implementation of innovative activities. In this context, the innovation environment is understood as the totality of all socio-economic subsystems that provide access to various resources and provide one or another support to the participants in innovation.

The structure of the most significant socio-economic subsystems of the innovation environment includes the following elements:

- production and technological infrastructure (technological): knowledge production system, scientific research;
- enterprises prepared for the use of innovative technologies;
- system of realization of innovative achievements;

- information subsystem: databases and knowledge, access centers, analytical, statistical, information centers;

- expert and consulting subsystem: organizations engaged in the provision of services on intellectual property, standardization, certification, as well as consulting centers, both general and specializing in certain areas;

- system of technological audit, marketing, etc.;
- human capital (staffing):
- working conditions (level of employment), income;

- medical care, demographic situation;
- financial support for innovative projects.

The functioning of the innovative environment of economic systems has specific features associated with the role of the state in maintaining and regulating its financial basis. The own environment of economic systems is part of the national innovation environment (internal innovation environment), which not only forms a strategy for the further development of the innovation environment, but also directly depends on the quality of the activities of certain subsystems.

The innovation system of the Republic of Uzbekistan currently includes:

- 1) reproduction of knowledge by conducting fundamental and exploratory research in the Republican Academy of Sciences, other academies of sciences with state status, as well as in the universities of the country;

- 2) conducting applied research and technological developments in state scientific centers of the country and scientific organizations of industry; introduction of scientific and technical results into production;

- 3) industrial and agricultural production of competitive innovative products;

- 4) development of the infrastructural component of the domestic innovation system;

- 5) training of personnel in organization and management in the field of innovation.

In Uzbekistan, innovation activity is supported by the state. This is done through the legal system, state and departmental funds, major projects and investment programs, taxation, and other instruments.

Considering the innovation environment from various angles, we can say that it allows you to increase the relationship between institutions, contributes to the creation of missing communications between the elements of the innovation system and accelerates the process of forming an innovation economy.

The main directions of the formation of the innovation environment in a strategically oriented economic system focus the totality of the development of the directions of the elements of the innovation environment.

Fig.1 Directions for the formation of an innovative environment

In order to accelerate the development of Uzbekistan on the basis of modern achievements of world science, innovative ideas, developments and technologies, the Innovative Development Strategy for 2019–2021 was approved, as well as targets for innovative development until 2030. At the same time, the main objectives of the Strategy to achieve the main goal are Uzbekistan's entry into the 50 leading countries of the world according to the Global Innovation Index by 2030.

One of the objectives of the Strategy is to strengthen the scientific potential and effectiveness of scientific research and development, to create effective mechanisms for integrating education, science and entrepreneurship for the wide implementation of the results of research, development and technological work. In addition, it is necessary to increase the investment of public and private funds in innovation, research, development and technological work, the introduction of modern and efficient forms of financing activities in these areas. In addition, it is necessary to ensure the protection of property rights, the creation of competitive markets and equal conditions for doing business, the development of public-private partnerships, as well as the creation of a sustainable socio-economic infrastructure.

There are a large number of reasons due to which the innovation environment cannot begin to form, or factors that slow down and negatively affect it. These

may include economic factors such as high price or lack of demand, factors specific to a particular region such as a lack of qualified personnel or knowledge, or legal barriers such as regulatory or taxation. Differences in the level of innovative activity can be different. The identification of key characteristics and factors that contribute to innovation activity, the formation of an innovation environment and the development of specific industries can help in understanding the innovation process in the country.

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